

Non-invasive dendrochronological analysis of the Holmedal epitaph, Bergen

Aoife Daly

2nd March 2017

Contents

THE HOLMEDAL EPITAPH, BERGEN.....	2
The wood	3
Results.....	4
Oak provenance	5
Literature	6

The Holmedal epitaph, Bergen

This research contributes to the research project, ‘After the Black Death: Painting and Polychrome Sculpture in Norway, 1350–1550’. The project is co-led by Noëlle Streeton and Tine Frøysaker, based in Conservation Studies, University of Oslo (UiO).

In November 2015, photographs for non-invasive dendrochronological analysis were taken of wood components of the Holmedal epitaph, Bergen, Norway (fig. 1). Measurements of the tree-rings from these photographs were made over subsequent occasions and the results of this is presented here.

Fig. 1. Holmedal epitaph, Bergen. View of the front of the object (photo Aoife Daly).

The wood

The epitaph is a single panel, made from three vertically placed oak boards. The panel is set in a frame. Thus, the end-grain of the three boards was not accessible for viewing.

In order to attain tree-ring measurements of the three boards, photographs were taken of the backs of the boards, at the top and bottom edges where a shallow bevel has been fashioned (fig. 2). The tree-rings were clearly visible on one of the boards, while two others presented difficulties.

The macro-photographs were marked up in Adobe Photoshop (version 11.0.2), and measured using the application “Able Image Analyser”. Here, a ruler in the photos is used to calibrate the picture,

and the measurements are made to 1/100mm precision. For calculation of the t-value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used, embedded in the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997).

Only the middle board (board 2) is dated (fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Holmedal epitaph, Bergen. The image of the bevel edge of board 1 showing the tree-rings (photo Aoife Daly).

Results

Board 1 is narrower than the other two boards. It contained 142 tree-rings but it could not be dated. Boards 2 and 3 are of very similar dimensions. Board 3 contains 218 tree-rings but the clarity of the tree-rings, using this non-invasive method, was not sufficient throughout the images attained. Despite several measurements of the tree-ring series this board still could not be dated. Board 2 contains 173 tree-rings and this tree-ring curve could be dated. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1318 to 1490. No sapwood was observed on the board so, allowing for missing

sapwood, the felling date of the oak tree that was used to make this board can be placed at **after** AD 1500.

The object is historically dated to c. 1520 (Bergen Museum) and the dendrochronological result fits neatly with this historical dating.

Fig. 3. Holmedal epitaph, Bergen. Bar diagram, dendrochronological dating of board 2 from the Holmedal epitaph. The bar shows the chronological position of the tree-ring curve. The arrow at the right-hand side indicates the date for the felling of the tree used for making the board. As no sapwood is preserved, the dating is *terminus post quem*. Colour shading indicates the possible interpretation of the results (illustration: Aoife Daly).

Filenames	-	-	Z152002a	
-	start	dates	AD 1318	
-	dates	end	AD 1490	
H11EOM01	AD 1260	AD 1495	7.12	Bordesholmer Altar 10 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
OM040004	AD 1156	AD 1597	5.42	Baltic 1 64 timbers (Hillam & Tyers 1995)
B0352M02	AD 1386	AD 1489	5.37	Roskilde Stændertorvet barrel staves 3 timbers (Daly 2015)
00751M01	AD 1113	AD 1463	4.95	Vejdyb Ship 14 trees (Daly 1997)
H137PM01	AD 1408	AD 1555	4.84	Seeth Haus 3 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
Z084M001	AD 1309	AD 1435	4.63	Skaftö wreck barrel 7 timbers (Daly 2013)
OLUN0020	AD 621	AD 1723	4.32	Lund oak (Eggertsson pers comm)
SM000012	AD 1125	AD 1720	4.26	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
Z054m001	AD 1235	AD 1448	4.23	Ostsee VII ship planks 5 timbers (Daly 2010)
BATM001_B3	AD 1342	AD 1599	4.16	Batavia Western Australia Baltic3 group 6 timbers (Daly 2016)
skodborg	AD 1268	AD 1540	4.11	Skodborghus & Møllebakken (Christensen pers comm)
midtjy17	AD 536	AD 1980	4.09	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)

Table 1. Holmedal epitaph, Bergen. The table shows the correlation (t-value) between the tree ring curve from plank 2 and a range of tree ring datasets. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Oak provenance

The correlation (t-test) between the tree-ring curve from board 2 and a range of tree-ring data for oak is shown in table 1. The material is dating with a range of chronologies from Northern Europe achieving highest correlation with a tree-ring dataset from the Bordesholmer Altar which has been shown to have been fashioned from Southern Baltic oak, and with a large chronology named 'Baltic 1' which is also built from art-historical materials whose origin is in the Southern Baltic region.

As the dendrochronological analysis indicates that the oaks used had grown in the Southern Baltic region a sapwood estimate for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)) is used.

filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra end	Ave ring width (mm)	interpretation / felling
Z1520012	Holmedal epitaph Bergen board 3	218			T	G	0	N	H1	1,35	undated
Z152002a	Holmedal epitaph Bergen board 2	173	AD 1318	AD 1490	T	G	0	N	H1	1,63	after AD 1500
Z152003b	Holmedal epitaph Bergen board 1	142			T	G	0	N	H1	1,11	undated
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, ph.d.				2nd March 2017							

Table 3. Holmedal epitaph, Bergen. List of objects analysed.

Literature

- Baillie, M.G.L. and Pilcher, J.R., 1973: A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bulletin* 33, 7-14.
- Bråthen, A., 1982. Dendrokronologisk serie från västra Sverige 813-1975. *Rapport Riksantikvarieämbetet och Statens historiska museer* 1982:1. Stockholm.
- Daly, A., 1997. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af skibsvrag fra Vejdyb udfor Hals, Aalborg Amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport* 1997 : 12, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2007. *Timber, Trade and Tree-rings. A dendrochronological analysis of structural oak timber in Northern Europe, c. AD 1000 to c. AD 1650*. Ph.D. thesis submitted February 2007, University of Southern Denmark.
- Daly, A., 2010. Ostsee VII Fpl 92, Meklenburg-Vorpommern, Germany. *dendro.dk rapport nr.* 2010 : 35
- Daly, A., 2013. Barrels from the Skaftö shipwreck. *Dendro.dk rapport nr.* 2013 : 4, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2015. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømmer fra Stændertorvet, Roskilde, ROM 3224. *dendro.dk rapport* 2015 : 34, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2016. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from Batavia, a Dutch ship, wrecked off the Australian coast. *Dendro.dk report* 2016: 58, Copenhagen.
- Hillam, J. and Tyers, I., 1995. Reliability and repeatability in dendrochronological analysis: tests using the Fletcher archive of panel-painting data. *Archaeometry* 37, p. 395-405.
- Tyers, I.G., 1997. Dendro for Windows Program Guide, *ARCUS Report* 340, Sheffield.
- Wazny, T., 1990. *Aufbau und Anwendung der Dendrochronologie für Eichenholz in Polen*. PhD Thesis. Universität Hamburg, pp. 213.

This report is produced as part of the project **TIMBER** (Northern Europe's timber resource - chronology, origin and exploitation). The project has received funding from the European Research

Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 677152) and is based at the University of Copenhagen. Timber in Northern Europe is being studied to attain a precise chronology for the material evidence for trade of timber from c. AD 1200 to 1700, to map the trade in this construction material, to show the regional and temporal fluctuations in timber exploitation and availability through time and to discover the origin of so-called 'Baltic' oak.

